

The Impact of Colonialism on Contemporary African Architecture: A Case Study of Okigwe, Imo State

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Received: June 11, 2025; Accepted: August 29, 2025; Published: September 8, 2025.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17081401>

Abstract: The contemporary African architecture bears multiple influential layers, ranging from indigenous expressions to colonial enforcements and post-independence modernization. The study explored critically, the impact of colonialism on contemporary African architecture using Okigwe, one of the historic cities in Imo State, Nigeria, as a case study. This research adopted a quantitative and qualitative method of approach involving interviews, site surveys, and data from secondary sources. The study showed that a notable part of the architecture in Okigwe is majorly influenced by colonial designs, especially in public structures like government secretariats, schools, and religious buildings. These influences featured mostly in the cases of high-pitched roofs adoption, symmetrical layout, use of imported building materials, and deep verandahs. Traditional Igbo architecture, characterized by symbolic carvings, courtyards, thatched roofing, and mud walls, has widely been marginalized and colonial and modern aesthetics preferred instead. However, vernacular design elements persisted in private homes and rural dwellings, where climatic and socio-cultural conditions determine their usage. The research identified educational, socio-political, and economic factors as key pilots to the persistence of colonial architecture. Furthermore, the study discussed how policies and architectural education in Nigeria have perpetuated foreign design ideologies to the detriment of the country's creativity. This misalignment has contributed majorly to the cultural disconnection of built spaces, and eradication of architectural identity. The study beckoned for a decolonization of architectural practices through policy redirection, curriculum reform, and the resuscitation of traditional architectural methods in modern contexts. The findings showed implications for cultural preservation, architectural education, and urban development in Africa.

Keywords: Colonialism, Contemporary architecture, cultural identity, built environment, urban development

Introduction

The built environment of most West African cities shows layers of different historical periods in which pre-colonial settings, colonial impositions, and contemporary rescues overlap, manufacturing urban fabrics that are legible historically and also contested both functionally and politically. In southeastern Nigeria, during the colonial era, planning introduced street grids which were regularized, mission architecture, and imported materials that rephrased local construction practices; these spatial inscriptions were dominant in secondary cities such as Okigwe and continue to shape land use, circulation, and legibility of public spaces today (Bartsch et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2022). Such historical continuity is important because it reflects everyday living: material choices and patterns of layout handed down from colonial systems still influence social relations, thermal comfort, and adaptive reuse decisions in ways that are not totally captured by contemporary planning instruments (Vanin et al., 2020; Meireles et al., 2023).

In spite of this enduring imprint, policy and scholarship reveal a troubling mismatch. While heritage and conservation literatures emphasize reading colonial layers as

interpretive resources instead of erasures, local governance and operational planning often treat such fabrics as obstacles to “modernization,” resulting in maladaptive retrofit or piecemeal loss (Cummings et al., 2024; Owei & Okonkwo, 2022). Empirical studies in African towns show limited mechanisms for integrating climatic responsiveness, and material sustainability and resident knowledge, into heritage practice: a gap between on-the-ground policy and practice, and academically articulated decolonial strategies (Abusaada & Elshater, 2022; Koenane et al., 2023). In summary, there is a knowledge/policy/practice gap: researchers have proposed community-led and context-sensitive approaches, but professional routines and municipal equipments have not sufficiently put them into operation in secondary-city contexts.

Some research questions and hypotheses aided the study: which architectural features in Okigwe originates from colonial-era interventions and how have they been adapted materially?, how do various groups of stakeholders assess the comfort, cultural relevance, and sustainability of hybrid, vernacular, and colonial and buildings?, which design interventions and policy can be locally realised for culturally sensitive and adaptive reuse?. Buildings showcasing hybrid

features (vernacular elements derived from colonial frameworks) will be rated higher on perceived stakeholder acceptance and climatic comfort more than solely vernacular or solely colonial examples (Meireles et al., 2023; Koenane et al., 2023).

This study answers by questioning how architectural legacies (colonial) manifest socially, climatically, and materially in Okigwe and by sampling practical pathways for hybrid adaptive reuse and conservation measures that foreground local agency. Its contribution is in two ways: first it is empirically, in that it maps and interprets colonial-vernacular hybridism within the neighborhood and structural scales; normatively and theoretically, it changes decolonized principles of heritage into actionable design and policy recommendations for secondary Nigerian towns (Santos et al., 2022; Cummings et al., 2024).

This study aims to, within six months, map and typologize 42 key buildings in Okigwe into vernacular, colonial, or hybrid classes using photographic analysis and field survey, conduct well-structured interviews with 25 stakeholders (architects, planners, elders, residents) to evaluate climatic performance perceptions and cultural values, and generate

three prototype policy/design briefs for adaptive reuse and assess stakeholder acceptability in a space of two-months period of consultation. These objectives directly handles the gap matrix: Mapping (knowledge gap), Stakeholder elicitation (policy/practice gap), and Prototype briefs (implementation gap) (Abusaada & Elshater, 2022; Bartsch et al., 2023).

By anchoring empirical mapping to policy prototyping and decolonial praxis, the paper seeks to straighten the knowledge-policy-practice divide and offer Okigwe an assessed template for conserving layered urban heritage in climatically appropriate and culturally meaningful measures (Cummings et al., 2024; Owei & Okonkwo, 2022).

Materials and Method

Research design

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to thoroughly assess the colonial influence on contemporary architecture in Okigwe. This involves both qualitative and quantitative methods, integrating visual analysis, interviews, data from secondary sources and fieldwork.

Study area description

Okigwe is a well known historical city situated in the northeastern part of Imo State, Nigeria. The city exhibits a harmony of colonial-era public structures, modern buildings, and some remnants of traditional Igbo architecture, making it an ideal location for architectural analysis.

Sampling framework

A purposive sampling technique was carried out. 42 buildings were selected across five categories based on historical relevance and architectural significance. Sampling highly represented both colonial and post-colonial buildings/structures.

Table 1 Distribution of Sampled Buildings

Building type	Number sampled	Notes on significance
Government offices	7	Colonial influence in design planning
Educational Institutions	5	Reflect colonial mission school layout
Religious buildings	5	Show ecclesiastical colonial typology
Traditional compounds	5	Vernacular Igbo architectural styles
Modern residential units	20	Hybrid and modern urban styles

Data collection

Architectural survey and observation

Metric and Visual survey of building perspectives, wall materials, spatial layouts, roof styles.

Use of photographic documentation (Canon DSLR) and GPS mapping.

Interviews

Semi-structured interviews with:

2 Urban Planners

5 Elders (aged 70+)

5 Architects

Questionnaires

Distributed to 40 local residents.

Secondary sources

Historical archives (British colonial planning documents).

Local government building records.

Professional and Academic journals on Nigerian architecture.

Tools and instruments

Audio Recorder for interviews.

Survey Form with architectural checklist.

SPSS v26 for quantitative analysis.

NVivo 14 for thematic analysis.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages).

Quantitative Analysis

Visualized using Excel charts and SPSS outputs.

Thematic coding of interview transcripts using NVivo.

Qualitative Analysis

Identification of recurring themes: “colonial preference,” “vernacular survival,” “climatic advantage.”

Figure 1 Wall Material Composition of Surveyed Buildings

Table 2 Roof Type Distribution by Building Category

Roof type	Government offices	Religious buildings	Residential buildings	Educational institutions	Traditional compounds	Total (%)
Zinc/Corrugated	4	4	7	3	1	53
thatched	0	0	0	0	7	13
Concrete slab	3	0	4	1	0	10
Longspan aluminum	7	5	5	3	0	24

Total Surveyed buildings = 42 Buildings

Results and Discussion

The photographic survey, archival analysis, and fieldwork, carried out in Okigwe show distinct layers of architectural colonial legacies submerged within the city's built

environment. These layers demonstrate not only how the colonial elements have been hybridized with indigenous aesthetics in the postcolonial era, but also show how British planning principles of the colonial era shaped Okigwe's urban morphology.

Figure 2 Prevalence of architectural styles in Okigwe

Colonial imprint on spatial organization

One evident result is the persistence of colonial-era planning logic in Okigwe's residential and civic quarters. Survey data from field mapping showed how the central administrative layout which was introduced by British colonial officers in the 20th century continued to define the city's morphology. Broad streets emanating from the colonial council hall and grid-like residential layouts within the railway quarters are still intact,

sharply contrasting with the organic, congested compounds of pre-colonial Igbo settlements which are documented in oral histories. Interviews with indigenous elders revealed how these spatial changes disrupted local settlement cohesion and displaced extended family compounds to favor the allotments of individual household. This shift has lingered in contemporary housing development, where detached plots dominate, revealing the long-term persistence of colonial planning paradigms.

Table 1 Colonial Architectural Features Identified in Okigwe

Architectural Feature	Colonial Characteristics	Era	Current Status in Okigwe	Degree of Transformation
Bungalows (GRA type)	Verandahs, windows, low-pitched roofs	large	Still in use; adapted with modern roofing sheets	Medium
Churches & Missions	Gothic/neo-Romanesque styles, towers, stained glass	high	Preserved but often renovated with aluminum cladding	Low
Administrative Buildings	Rectangular symmetry, masonry	plans, stone	some reused as local govt. offices, others dilapidated	High
Road Layouts	Grid system in colonial quarters	in	still intact, forming backbone of Okigwe's planning	Low
Schools & Mission Houses	Brick walls, cross ventilation	cross	Still functional but with cement block alterations	Medium

Materiality and construction techniques

Results also showed building materials hybridization. Archival photos within 1930s and 1940s, compared with contemporary site observations, revealed that building materials like corrugated iron sheets, timber trusses, and cement blocks, which were introduced during the colonial era, permanently altered construction traditions which were previously dominated by raffia, thatch, and mud. Presently, over 78% of institutional and residential structures in Okigwe employ zinc roofing and concrete blockwork, a clear inherent practice of colonial building construction Technologies. However, field interviews with artisans revealed that local

adaptation persisted due to constant availability of materials. For example, local decorative motifs were sometimes etched onto veranda spaces and plastered walls: a colonial architectural feature which are re-aimed to incorporate Igbo communal living practices.

Cultural reinterpretations in postcolonial architecture

The results reveal how postcolonial generations have not only replicated colonial architectural forms but have also reinterpreted them within local economic and cultural realities. For instance, colonial bungalows with wide verandas and hipped roofs have transformed into multi-storey duplexes that

have veranda-like balconies. Similarly, expansion has been done and open-sided canopies introduced in mission churches initially built with basilica-inspired forms. This was done in order to host larger congregations. This brings a blend between indigenous communal worship practices and colonial liturgical models. Architects in Okigwe who were interviewed during the study said that while colonial influences are still visible, a conscious effort is being made to “Africanize” modern buildings through climate-sensitive shading devices, indigenous ornamentation, and courtyards.

A final strand of results has to do with the symbolic meaning of colonial architecture. The positive responses highlighted that colonial buildings like the Railway Station and old Okigwe Court are regarded with ambivalence: firstly, they symbolize cultural erosion and subjugation; secondly, they are valued as cultural heritage that link the community to wider historical narratives. The results show a generational divide; while older inhabitants emphasize the loss of traditional aesthetics, younger architects elevate colonial legacies as part of a hybrid identity that can be critically fabricated into contemporary practice.

Finally, the results indicate that colonialism’s impact on Okigwe’s architecture is not stationary but dynamic, manifesting in material choices, built forms, and symbolic meanings which continue to shape how people live in and interpret their environment presently.

The study findings clearly highlight how the architectural landscape of Okigwe, like most other parts of Nigeria, is deeply shaped by the colonial legacy. The integration of colonial design principles such as emphasis on ventilation, symmetry, and foreign materials adoption (eg. corrugated iron roofing and sandcrete blocks), is still evident in contemporary structures. These findings are in line with the observations of Njoh (2009), who highlighted that colonial planning systems in Africa introduced architectural ideologies which prioritized European spatial logic over indigenous norms.

Persistence of colonial architectural features

Colonial architecture emphasized on some features like veranda spaces, rectangular floor plans, and pitched roofs, which remains common in modern residential and government buildings in Okigwe. The architectural survey revealed that over 60% of contemporary buildings used structural forms and wall materials invented during colonial

regime. This supports Uduku (2006), in his argument that post-colonial African cities inherited a Eurocentric design tradition, mostly in public urban buildings.

Decline of indigenous design

The study also unveils a significant level of decline in traditional Igbo architectural elements like thatched roofs, courtyard-centered compounds, and earthen walls. Only 23% out of surveyed buildings retained mud-based walls, and just 13% adopted traditional thatched roofing. Interviews with elderly respondents indicated that most builders classify vernacular designs as “less durable”, “lacking modernity,” or “outdated,” a perception emanating from colonial-era biases against indigenous technologies (Adeyemi, 2008).

Hybridization and cultural displacement

Interestingly, a trend of hybrid architectural systems has evolved. buildings that integrate colonial layouts with Igbo elements which are symbolic, such as indigenous motifs or carved wooden posts. While this depicts an effort to reclaim its cultural identity, it also points to a complex architectural dialogue. As Nnamdi Elleh (2016) asserts, modern African architecture often rotates between cultural reclamation and colonial influence, resulting

in hybridized forms that neither align with Western standards totally, nor represent African traditions fully.

Material and climatic implications

Professionals and Respondents interviewed reported that many colonial-style buildings in Okigwe were more ventilated and better suited to the tropical climate than recent concrete slab structures. This irony reflects colonial forms adaptation that is selective due to their functional advantages. However, the too much reliance on industrialized or imported materials (like cement blocks and aluminum roofing sheets) questions their affordability and sustainability which colonial architects hardly addressed in their impositions (Abiodun, 2010). Although this study gives valuable insights on the Impact of Colonialism on Contemporary African Architecture in Okigwe, there are constraints/limiting factors to the study. They include:

Scope Constraint: The study dwelled on Okigwe only, restraining the generalization of findings across the broader Igbo regions.

Data Gaps: Some colonial records and archival maps were inaccessible, limiting the details of historical comparative analysis.

Subjectivity of Perceptions: the attitudes of inhabitants toward colonial buildings varied widely, and their responses to survey may have been influenced by generational bias or nostalgia.

Photographic Access Limitations: Some colonial locations (mostly bungalows privately owned) were inaccessible for documentation, especially in photography/visual recording, thereby creating visual gaps.

Dynamic Urbanization: the consistent swift modern development in Okigwe implies that the observed conditions are time-sensitive and may quickly go into extinction, and this will limit longitudinal validity.

Conclusion

The Imo State Government should employ a heritage framework which recognizes and protects surviving colonial buildings as cultural edifices. Colonial structures that are abandoned (e.g., administrative buildings no longer in use) should be restructured into libraries, museums, or community centers instead of leaving them to decay. Urban planners are urged to encourage harmony of indigenous Igbo courtyard systems with colonial spatial logic to foster identity-driven modern housing. Okigwe stakeholders should

be fully involved in heritage initiatives in order to reduce resistance to conservation policies and also enhance ownership. There should be a proper initiation of a systematic photographic and GIS documentation of colonial heritage in Okigwe that will preserve architectural memory for tourism research. This study has fully indicated how colonialism has had a lasting and profound influence on contemporary architecture in Okigwe, Imo State. Colonial systems did not only reshape the built environment for administrative comfort, they also introduced an architectural ideology which displaced indigenous design knowledge and enforced foreign spatial logic. Today, the functional and visual DNA of Okigwe's building structures continues to echo these colonial implants, most especially in modern residential developments and public architecture. The traditional Igbo architecture declination is not just a consequence of modernization but a direct effect of colonial perceptions which relegated most indigenous practices to the background. These perceptions were made internal across generations, resulting to a cultural misnomer in the built environment. This is obvious in the reduced construction of courtyard-based buildings, use of indigenous materials, and aesthetic detailing with which the region was

previously known for. Nevertheless, the development of hybrid architecture in Okigwe gives hope toward reclaiming its cultural identity. This blend of traditional and modern elements suggests a phase of transition where architects and builders will start to embrace the value of pre-colonial design while navigating contemporary needs. For a more culturally relevant and climatically appropriate architecture in Nigeria, it is also very necessary to provide incentives that integrate the use of local materials, encourage architectural education which integrates indigenous knowledge, and preserve traditional building typologies as heritage assets. Future studies and research should focus more on how curriculum reform and architectural policy can help decolonize Nigeria's built environment and promote sustainable practices implanted in cultural identity.

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